

THE ROLE OF WORKS ON MODERN THEMES IN IMPROVING THE SKILL OF THE ACTOR

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Abstract. *In this article, on the example of the play "Seven cries", the role of works on a modern topic in improving the skill of an actor is explained. It is assumed that the essence of the drama consists in revealing the contradictions of reality, embodied in conflicts that determine the development of the movement of the work, internal conflicts inherent in the personality of the characters.*

Keywords: *actor, director, drama, theater, play, tandem, stage, dramatist, character, performance, dramatism, scenery.*

Introduction. The essence of the drama is to reveal the contradictions of reality embodied in the conflicts that determine the development of the action of the work, in the internal conflicts inherent in the personalities of the characters. Throughout the history of the theater, the plots, forms and styles of dramaturgy have changed. Initially, myths served as the subject of the image, in which the spiritual experience of mankind was summarized. The turning point in the drama came with reference to real history and domestic conflicts. Plots began to feature grand heroic events and characters in drama. In a drama, the event unfolds not through internal reflection, but through external action. In addition, all events take place in the present.

The play "Seven cries" is based on the play of Alejandro Cassona in the genre of psychological drama. On New Year's Eve, the captain's assistant made a Christmas tree and told the captain about his childhood. One by one, the cyborgs begin to gather on the ship's deck. They flatter each other without knowing anything and talk about all kinds of nonsense. There are seven main characters in the play. They are all main characters.

Mr.Garrison - the character played by Erkin Komilov. The character is nervous, angry, speaks sharply, is always dissatisfied with something, suspicious of something. He thinks only evil. Mr.Garrison repeats that there has been a loss of radio communication for three days, that the ship is on a different course, that there is something to be said. Others ignore him and laugh at him. But there was life in Mr.Garrison's air. The ship was indeed sailing towards death.

Mr.Garrison is the owner of large industrial enterprises, oil, arms dealer. According to the description of the captain (Y.Ahmedov), it is homeless. Indeed, those who look at the war with ordinary eyes and sell weapons to everyone will never have a homeland. Because they have nothing to do with peace. The more wars, the more profits. Mr.Garrison is also indifferent to the fate of people and does not care about the opinions of others. Always wear a crown. Only approves of his opinion.

Members of the upper class repent before death. Only one person does not repent. He is Garrison. Unable to bear the psychological pressure, he commits suicide. Garrison - Erkin Komilov hides his relationship with Mrs.Sabalo (N. Mahmudova) for several years. Nobody notices this until Mrs.Sabalo repents and confesses. He won't admit it even when all is revealed. Because guilt, conscience, courage were not characteristic of Garrison. Garrison paces the deck

impatiently until the captain makes the announcement. It goes against everyone's opinion. Accuses of indifference and lightness. What worries him is to get rid of this "old cage" as soon as possible. He was very worried about the price of oil on the stock exchange. The young journalist reacts strongly to Juan's (B.Muhammadkarimov) jokes. The actor said, "I know you don't like me, I'm very happy about it. But I don't like you that much either," she openly says that she doesn't like Juan with a cigarette in her hand.

The captain gathers everyone on deck and finally tells them what awaits them. The war has begun. The captain was ordered to distract enemy submarines. For this purpose, the captain ordered the ship to steer in the direction where the submarines were sailing. Third class passengers are not told about this.

The reason he told the upper class was that he wanted them to repent before he died. Mr.Garrison - Erkin Komilov, had no intention of repenting. He did not accept his fate like others. In the effort to save himself by making a way, that was the side that was different from others. When Santiago Sabalo (G.Hojiev) was drinking wine, when Professor (H.Nurmatov) was quietly talking, Baron Adolfo (T. Saidov) was busy with himself, Mr.Garrison could not find a place to put himself. Palubaga was walking from place to place, trying to talk to members of the third class, trying to get in touch with acquaintances. He encouraged his companions to resist. After hearing that the captain's men are likely to fire on him, he becomes overwhelmed. He looks at the captain so sharply that if he has a gun, he will shoot him.

As Juan said, Mr. Garrison was a man who sold guns to whomever he could. "All you have to do is sell, sell, sell. Now Garrison's torpedo blows up Mr.Garrison. "This time the truth will be decided". Juan's words were absolutely true. Mr. Garrison was never interested in the fate of people. His eyes are filled with hatred and resentment towards those around him.

If he stays, everyone will drown and only he will survive.

Mr.Garrison is Erkin Komilov, who does not want to suffer alone. Although he knows that rebellion is useless, he wants to convey the message to the third class. Then Garrison's cowardice is unknown among the many confused people.

Love feelings begins to blossom between Juan and the senorita. The professor was right about one thing: "At the gates of hell, sir, death gives way to love". Baranessa Nina (S.Yunusova) wants to confess her sins, as the captain said.

The emotions of the heroes begin to rise. Now unnerve them. They believe that there is no need to hide anything more. Mercedes Sabalo introduces Garrison as her role. But Garrison immediately denies it. Garrison's inferiority is revealed once again in this scene. Having an affair with a married woman, he again freely denies it. Mercedes thanks him for seeing his real face, even though it's too late. Garrison leaves the scene, unable to respond to Mercedes' insults. Santiago Sabalo also tells his past and pulls lightly.

Turgun Azizov, the director of the play "Seven Cries" in his book "My directorial works" expresses the following thoughts about Erkin Komilov's performance of the role of Garrison: "Garrison is one of the complex characters in the work. This role went to Erkin Komilov, one of the leading actors of the theater. For Garrison, man, his destiny, is empty and useless. For him, everything is measured by money and wealth. He needs a war machine, not a man. Erkin Komilov and Ravshan Joraev created the image of such a villain in their own way. From the very first words of Garrison-Komilov, the audience notices that he is a vile person, and hates him. Personally, I'm happy with his performance. There's only one scene that doesn't satisfy me, and that's Garrison's

suicide scene. There was no heart-shattering explosion here. I explained too much, it didn't seem like it. Sometimes it happens".

Erkin Komilov can find and reveal the truth of the negative characters he created. Along with Mr. Garrison. Garrison loves himself so much that he only puts himself first. All the characters in Pesa were the main ones. But Erkin Komilov brings Garrison to the fore with his actions on stage. Garrison could be called a bully. He is so proud that he doesn't even want to suffer and die. Garrison shoots himself - an easy death - while the other heroes beg and accept their fate and drown. Because drowning is a painful death. Garrison, who never suffered in his life, only loved himself, chooses the easy way even before his death. When Senor Sabalo, Mercedes, Nina, Adolfo, and the Professor all repent and regret their sins, only Garrison remains proud.

Because he did not regret anything, he always considered himself entitled to everything.

Erkin Komilov plays another character similar to the character of Garrison in the play "Seven cries" in the play "Bir qadam yo'l" - ("One step way"). Their similarity was that both of them are characters who only think about their own interests, love material wealth, and are not interested in the fate of others.

"One step way" is a play about sons who did not take their father to the place he dreamed of for a lifetime, loyalty to promises, honesty, pride, and dreams. The events of the play take place against the backdrop of three brothers' pursuit of their problems, taking their aging father to Samarkand. Big brother Jora - T. Mominov is a person who lived in poverty only because of work, lived honestly and did not betray anyone's rights. The middle son, Shakir - Erkin Komilov, became very rich after the black drug trade, and he was respected and respected everywhere.

Erkin Komilov - who emphasizes Shakir's showing people on their toes, jokingly shoots a gun, makes fun of his brother and laughs, it is obvious that these unusual actions are the result of dollars earned by criminal means. The third son Kasim is U.Tillaev returned from the Afghan war in mourning, quarrelsome, indifferent to his future. The three sons just look at this old man's dream, thinking of taking their father to Samarkand, one step away. One would say that I don't have time, the other would have important work to do. And for another, there is no difference at all. At the beginning of the play, the old father tries to give the sapling to one of his sons, but none of them take it from the father. It was a symbolic dream of his. No boy would want to take this little dream on his neck. When he was young, the family was suffering from childhood pain, when he got old and became dependent on his legs, he realized how quickly life passed.

When the brothers talk, it becomes clear how different their world views and principles are. The elder brother lives only by honest work and does not pay bribes to anyone, so he does not betray anyone's rights, and takes responsibility for people's fate. He believed that the life of a person who has to serve the people will be spent hungry.

Erkin Komilov - Shokirjon left the village when he was young saying he would not return until he became rich. No one knew how he got rich. His opinion is that the only freedom is money. He used to say that honor and conscience can be bought with money. Although he hated corrupt officials, he did business with them. Adam would not choose; he would talk to them out of necessity. As his brother described, he would come to the village once a year and disappear again. Every time he came, he would promise to take his father to Samarkand, and he would finish his work and leave with empty promises. Father's dream for them was just a simple desire to be pampered. Shakir's real purpose for coming to the village is different. In the course of the play, his coming to see his family is one thing, and another is revealed.

At first glance, going to Samarkand is a step, even if the father could not go to Samarkand after walking this way all his life. A human child comes into this world as a spring. When he thinks he is a spring and turns into a river, he thinks he is a spring and turns into a sea, and he does not realize that his life has come to an end. Then he found out that he couldn't get out between the two shores, he was longing for something, waiting for something, and just ran. That's when the desire to dream appears. The father did not even notice that his life had passed so quickly. When father moved to these lands, there was not a single blackened tree. He made these lands an endless garden, and spent his life in working hard. Therefore, he could not go anywhere except the district center. It suddenly became his dream to go to Samarkand, to visit the footsteps of good people. In addition to the themes of dreams, conscience, honesty, and pride, the play also includes themes of homesickness, loyalty to the homeland, and love. Mohammad Chagana, a guest from abroad, wanted to return to the soil where his grandfather's navel blood was spilled, he missed his homeland very much. Eshmamatov did not hesitate to emphasize that "your return to the homeland is an honor of independence". He himself was an accomplice in the drug trade, and instead of the governorship, he preached at meetings and events and talked about serving the country with loyalty. That's why Shakir called him the devil. Shakir's language is the same. He does not praise anyone too much. He doesn't spare people by telling them everything to their faces.

Every character had pain inside that they couldn't tell anyone. Saodat (S. Rametova) regretted that his life was spent only in hard work without leaving this village, and he envied its charm. The wife of another brother (G.Zokirova) was angry that her husband sent her son on a trip, as if selling heroin was not enough. No one but her could manage to live hating her husband every day. For twenty years, she looked at her husband as if she were looking at him, she did not let Shakir come close to her boundaries. No matter where Shakir went, everyone was staring at him. Only his wife would not surrender to him, because she did not love him at all. Nevertheless, Shakir continued to live with this woman. At first glance, the husband looks at her, loves her and loves her, what can he not do? Because Shakir possessed his wife by force, she felt nothing but hatred for him.

In the drama, vices such as neglecting human inclinations and not appreciating people in time are reflected in the example of the complicated fate of an old man who worked hard and lived honestly. The work shows the spirit of the old man and his sons, who dreamed of seeing and visiting Samarkand all his life, but due to his shortness of hand, later being preoccupied with life worries, and then the neglect of his children, he did not see the city near him and his sons.

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